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Student-Centered Education of Primary General Education Teachers for the Realization of Personal Potential in Profession and Career

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Abstract

The present research is interesting due to the existence of new approaches to the development of competence of a modern teacher which require transition from a knowledge paradigm of higher education to the student-centered paradigm and closer attention to the realization of personal potential of future teachers in profession and career. From this perspective, the present article addresses expansion of the system of student-centered education of primary general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in career and also, the description of learning environment which is created for the realization of this process. Core research method is a system approach which analyzes the process of education of primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in future profession and it should be studied as a comprehensive integrity of all its parts and on all levels of structural hierarchy of the process. The present article determines organizational and academical conditions for student-centered education of primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession. In the present article conceptual basis and a structural model of student-centered education of primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession were developed. The article contains materials, which can help to resolve the following issues: conflict of such factors as school needs of self-learning teachers and real-life willingness of normal universities graduates to continuously improve themselves; conflict between dominating group training method of professional education and individual student-centered form of development of professional skills; the conflict between objective needs of general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession, and poor readiness of learning environment and technologies which could allow young teachers to realize these needs; the conflict between the objective need of developing the willingness of general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession and poor theoretical development and methodical sufficiency of the studied process. Practical implication of results, contained in the present article, is technology and instructional guidelines development for the student-centered education of primary general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession.

Keywords: primary general education teachers, student-centered education, realization of personal potential in profession.

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Introduction

1.1. Topicality

Nowadays, developing of the teachers' willingness to realize their personal potential in profession is the latest trend in teachers' education. Main strategy of the modern education must contain personal development, professional self-identification and individuality of a teacher. Orientation of education towards the personal self-identification and creation of the environment is becoming the goal of the whole education. This fact is secured in the Law on Education of the Russian Federation. Due to social changes of modern society, new requirements to the content and technology of training of new teachers appear. Reasonably, it is possible to suppose knowledge paradigm to be at the end of its resources: on the one hand, a continuously expanding amount of knowledge becomes literally impossible to comprehend; on the other hand, higher education does not only require that a future teacher should know a high amount of information. This refers to learning of the system of competences by future teacher and resolving the problem of the realization of personal potential in profession.

In accordance with analysis of scientific researches, methodical literature, practical aspects of teaching in schools, and our research, which included studying of 316 students of different levels of the Primary Education Pedagogy and Methodology Faculty of Novokuznetsk branch of Kemerovo State University (NFI KemGU) and 511 young teachers who have been working at schools up to 3 years, we can make a statement that democratic changes in education appear and new approaches and technologies are being theorized in order to resolve the present problems of teacher education; however, modern primary school teachers encounter certain problems in realization of their personal potential in profession. In our view, it happens due to the lack of opportunities that become available with the student-centered approach in preparing the future primary teachers to the realization of their personal potential in profession.

1.2. Literature analysis

Realization of personal potential problem is complex and interdisciplinary. Scientific literature analysis shows that the idea of realization of personal potential was born in the studies of Adler (2002), who claimed the "universal human striving for superiority". This idea was specified in the Maslow theory of self-actualization (Maslow, 1997), and the concept of a fully functioning person by Rodgers (2011), as well as orientation of individual to the understanding of their individuality and variation from others due to revelation and realization of their needs by Fromm (2018).

Ways and methods of realization of personal potential in certain social and cultural conditions are studied in the works of Asmolov (1990), conditions of effective realization of personal potential are studied in the works of Abulkhanova-Slavskaya(1980), Brushlinskiy (1994), Rubinshtejn (1997).

The present article presents several concepts of student-centered education based on the works of Alekseev (1997), Bondarevskaya (1995), Bouehn (1992), Lavrikova (1998), Serikov (1999), Yakimanskaya (1996). The teachers training theories of the following scientists were analyzed: Kuzmina

(2001), Petrovskiy (1981), Sharshov (2000). The pedagogical models of preparing of future primary teachers to the innovation activity were analyzed by: Buya (1997), Elkina (2007), Kanbekova (2003). The future teachers' professional growth and realization of personal potential were analyzed by: Lozovan & Elkina (2018) and Dolgodvorova (2000).

1.3. Challenges and problems

Nowadays some problems of researches in this field are not studied enough, such as researches of certain educational environment which helps to develop the willingness of primary school teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession on both content and technology levels; creative potential of students is not revealed and used enough; professional self-identity almost doesn't form correctly.

In accordance with the time analysis of modern teachers training, including primary teachers, the field has major problems and gaps. The most important are:

- Poor attention of university teachers to the willingness of students to realize their personal potential; lack of inspirational methods for personal and professional development as well as development of personal qualities for teaching (reflection, surgency, empathy)
- Future teachers training one-sidedness: they are trained just to have competences, but students are not taught for the development in intellectual, moral and professional way
- Training potential of future student-centered education of primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession is not used efficiently
- Teachers reflection that aims at realizing the experience and personal development by primary school teacher is not good enough

Analysis of main education programs in different pedagogical fields shows, that their connections between professional and pedagogical training and student's everyday life and realization of personal potential are underrated. Lack of professional training orientation to the professional standards requirements does not contribute to the development of future teacher's system vision of the upcoming work in school as well as the complex vision of teacher's work nature and opportunities for the realization of their personal potential in curricular, extra-curricular and professional activities at university.

Research methods

Research methods

The following methods were used in research process: theoretical methods, such as philosophical, psychological and pedagogical literature analysis, regulatory and curricular documents analysis, related papers and publications analysis, modeling and analogy; empiric methods, such as lesson observations, polling, interviewing, testing, expert assessment, teaching experience summarizing, pedagogical experiment; mathematical statistics methods.

Trial facilities of the research

Novokuznetsk branch (institute) of Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "Kemerovo State University" was the experimental base of the research.

Research stages

The research was made in three stages:

- On the first stage, the theoretical and experimental foundation analysis was made; the state of the problem of training primary general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession and career was studied; research vocabulary was improved; main components and content of

training future teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession and career were developed; criteria and formedness markers of this training were developed and specified; the experiment working plans were determined.

- On the second stage, didactic and methodical facilities for the training of future primary general education teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession and career were developed; Federal State Educational Standard for higher education in the field of Teacher Education was studied; main educational programs for primary education were analyzed; curriculum, psychological and pedagogical programs were projected, optional courses contents developed, learning environment for training of future primary teachers for realization of personal potential in profession were determined.

- On the third stage, the experiment was completed, collected data processing and analysis were made, research results were finally summarized and systematized, theoretical conclusions were drawn and specified; research materials were published.

Results

Due to the development of theoretical model of primary teachers' training for the realization of personal potential in career we defined "student-centered education orientation" phenomenon as follows: for student-centered education, individual is considered to be the goal of education process, the whole student-centered education of future teachers specifying their training for the realization of personal potential in profession, has specific goals, principles, contents and methods of education, and it aims to develop student teacher's personal potential.

We found out that while developing teaching goals in student-centered educational environment, the following aspects must be considered: conditions allowing the development of student personality; conditions allowing to complete socially important task which reflects social needs for certain personality and individuality; teacher's personal and professional attributes. In this regard, student-centered pedagogical education suggests developing future primary teachers' personal and professional attributes which are specified by characteristics of their professional activity, stated as their intensive personal development and raise of realization of their personal potential as the education process.

Defining the premises of student-centered training of the future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession we were considering the idea that such training must reflect the specifics of students' willingness for working in primary general education institution and features of training students for working in innovative conditions. Consequently, future teachers training aims at developing the following personal and professional attributes: critical and flexible thinking; the ability to use intuition and analysis in teaching thinking; understanding of uniqueness and individuality; aiming for professional success; need for making personal choices, creative activities and the ability to resolve professional challenges creatively; empathy and willingness to collaborate; interest for student personality; motivation for psychological and pedagogical diagnostics of primary school students; the pedagogical reflection ability; positive self-concept and self-esteem; comprehensive knowledge, intellect and teaching abilities. This complex of personal and professional attributes correlate to the personal attributes of an individual ready for realization of personal potential in career.

In regards of building the program for training future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in profession it is important to create student-based approach as the foundation of educational process because teaching activity transfers from knowledge paradigm to the student-centered paradigm. In our research conception, personal approach in training of future primary teachers includes correct

definition of the student's personality sphere as a specific professional education goal.

We defined the structure of willingness of future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential. This structure includes the following components: values and motivation; orientation and goals; contents and gnostic component; creativity and process; reflection and evaluation.

As for the motivation and values component, the value-based approach to the professional teaching is typical. The basics of a method are: knowledges about humanistic nature of teaching activities; forming the personal willingness to collaborate, including teacher's collaboration, with all parts of teaching and educational process, the ability to raise themselves, the ability for self-education and realization of personal potential in future profession. Acquirement of all these knowledges and skills supposes the following important personal and professional attributes: tolerance and love to children; civic consciousness; respect for the rights and freedoms, humanism, self-acceptance; empathy; optimism; teaching tact; willingness for changes.

As for the orientation and goals component, main points are: complex knowledge of methods of pedagogic goal-setting, forecasting and planning of education. If students gained all these qualities, they are able to develop responsibility, ambition and pedagogical intuition.

Contents and gnostic component consist of competencies and features allowing future primary general education teachers to reveal cognition. These features are forming a base for developing innovative professional skills and students' attitude to the teaching process, while doing practical training in educational institutes.

Creativity and action component designate the following features: having theoretical knowledges in the field of teaching creativity nature, utilization of practical usage of these knowledges, presence of pedagogical art in students' actions. Learning how to use creative teaching impacts developing of creativity authenticity, communicative and leadership skills and pedagogic improvisation.

Reflection and evaluation component includes analysis and reflection – competencies allowing to control and evaluate the process of teaching of primary school students. Positive attitude towards these actions impacts developing of pedagogical reflection, self-control and correct self-esteem.

Thus, contents of every component of future primary teachers' training for the realization of personal potential in profession include the experience and features, defining completeness of this training. The defined components of this training depend on each other and they have strong dialectical connection. This dependence is obvious when considering personal level of the willingness for the realization of personal potential in future profession.

We evaluated the level of readiness and the willingness of future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in future career. 95 undergraduates of the Primary Education Pedagogy and Methodology Faculty of Novokuznetsk branch of Kemerovo State University (NFI KemGU) took part in the research. All these students were interns in various educational institutions of the city of Novokuznetsk. Each component was evaluated from 1 up to 10 points. Results are as follows: values and motivation component: 7.76; orientation and goals component: 7.11; contents and gnostic component: 9.34; creativity and process: 8.58; reflection and evaluation: 8.37.

We defined main components of the technology of training future primary general education teachers for the realization of personal potential: realizing of their personal and professional qualities; developing of pedagogical goal-setting skills, planning and forecasting skills.

The process of student-centered training of the future teacher for the realization of personal potential was oriented for the resolution of the following issues: developing of the value-based attitude to the

professional pedagogical activities; providing future teachers with educational support in the self-actualization of personal and professional attributes; forming of the planning, goal-setting and forecasting experience for educational activities. This resolution for these issues required students to take part in reflection and identification activities. We consider these activities as a planning, comparing and classification modification.

Reflection and identification of educational activity is oriented to the subjective ideas of the certain personality. When doing this activity, the process of reflection and identification helps to balance professional teaching goals and future teachers' personal goals.

We realized ideas of student-centered education of future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in future profession using the following instructional methods: "method acting", analysis of pedagogical choice' situations, discussion, "supposing..." method, simulation exercise, and reflection methods.

Due to affect and thinking perception, "method acting" let students to "move" into the position of student or teacher. It helped to feel and realize their inner world. We aimed student's observation turns to self-observation and after this it was possible for them to associate themselves with educational activity part.

"Supposing..." method was oriented to solve pedagogical issues with different premises. While realizing this method, students were free to vary premises themselves. When discussing issues, we paid special attention to the pedagogic ground of the resolution options offered by students.

Pedagogical choice situation analysis method was used while discussing possible conditions for their successful realization. Issue content supposed asking students challenging questions which have to be analyzed. Students must have offered possible resolution option.

Discussion method allowed students to prove their view, to develop person-to-person interaction experience, and helped to increase students' motivation while pursuing teaching activities. In order to develop goal-setting skills and discussions participants were offered to consider the problem in regards of special behavior model and previously stated activity goal. At the same time, students had an opportunity to create discussion rules, and these rules were respected when "pedagogical forums" and "round table discussions" were held.

The imitation exercises method supposed the teacher to have the correct or best way to resolve the problem while case method didn't.

Reflection was formed due to the developmental talks method and self-observation method. This forming was provided with a help of the following questions: "How did it happen, that...?"; "Why did it go this way?"; "Which tasks were completed?", so on. Self-observation method included creation of personal teaching analysis, internship lessons analysis, and writing a self-report on internship results.

Discussion question

The research shows that the current training of primary general education teachers for realization of personal potential in the future career system contains potential possibility to help student form the willingness that we studied. However, here is a lack of didactical and methodical resources, so, there is a need for additional research in the field of primary teacher's realization of personal potential in future profession development while these students are at the postgraduate level in the career development system. However, the following scientists made a research on the development of the readiness of teachers working on the different levels of Russian educational system: Agavelyan & Agavelyan (1995),

Omelchenko, Chesnokova, & Agavelyan (2018), Soloveva & Zausenko (2015), Tarasova (2017), Chesnokova & Chesnokov (2015). The following specialists do the research in the field of student-centered educational process individualization technologies for teachers' universities: Bajborodova, Belkina, Gruzdev, & Gushhina (2018), Burlakova (2015), Gushhina (2016), Sedova (2017).

Conclusion

Analytical and experimental results of the development and realization of student-centered education of future primary teachers for the realization of personal potential in future career allow us to make the following conclusion:

- Motivation and goal module, contents and process module and reflection and evaluation module provide the creation of didactic and methodical system, oriented to the development of each component of future teacher willingness for the realization of personal potential in united and connected tasks, technological components and ways of collaboration of educational process subjects.
- Since methods, forms and resources that were used allow students to develop professional and personal qualities, necessary for the successful teaching work, didactic and methodical resources provide us with the possibility for training future teacher for the realization of personal potential
- The developed methodic orientation to the realization of student-centered educational paradigm provides actualization and development of future teachers subject teaching experience.

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